

Golden Nopales

by Pablo Angel Lugo

Golden Nopales (cactus)

This project was born a long time ago, with an extraordinary story about WWII and the Nazi concentration camps.

I once read something about a Jew survivor living in Mexico. She was shocked when she saw Mexicans eat cactus. She couldn't believe what she saw — Mexicans take off the thorns of the cactus and cook it, sometimes by itself and sometimes as part of more complex dishes; and that is not the end, because the plant is nutritious and healthy.

The nopales (cacti) are one of the species of *Cactaceae*. The Spanish brought it from the Americas to Europe. The surprising thing is how they assumed that, at most, the plant's usefulness was limited to being a "natural" fence for their castles.

The idea of how the conquerors brought the plant but not the learning about it, how they despised indigenous knowledge about indigenous land is creating now a big problem in Spain. The nopales or "chumbera" as they are called in Spain are now considered a plague in the Iberian Peninsula.

Golden Nopales is a tribute to all despised knowledge that has been eliminated by the Colonial Period. Golden Nopales is a way to reclaim ancient wisdom and fight for decolonisation, and to tell Old Europe that it is time to learn about other ways to live with nature.

Golden Nopal I

Gold leaves / Wood

20 x 10 x 18 cm

2019

Golden Nopal II

Acrylic / Wood

17 x 11 x 19 cm

2019

Golden Nopal III

Acrylic / Wood

12 x 10 x 14 cm

2019

Golden Nopal IV

Acrylic / Wood

12 x 10 x 13 cm

2019

Golden Nopal V

Acrylic / Wood

10 x 7 x 20 cm

2019

Golden Nopal VI

Acrylic / Wood

19 x 9 x 14 cm

2019

Golden Nopal VII

Acrylic / Wood

17 x 10 x 12 cm

2019

Golden Nopal VIII

Acrylic / Wood

12 x 9 x 18 cm

2019

Golden Nopal IX

Acrylic / Wood

14 x 10 x 15 cm

2019

Golden Nopal X

Acrylic / Wood

16 x 13 x 16 cm

2019

Golden Nopal XI

Acrylic / Wood

18 x 16 x 13 cm

2019

Pablo Angel Lugo is an artist of considerable international reputation and enviable academic background, born in Mexico City. His work has taken him worldwide and been exhibited likewise.

Pablo's speciality is in public art, but his vast artistic output includes paintings, drawings, engravings, sculptures, videos, performances, illustrations, graphic designs and cinematic collaborations.

His work has been exhibited in Mexico, Cuba, USA, UK, Spain, Colombia, France, Portugal, Argentina and Indonesia amongst other countries.

He has studied in Mexico and Spain, earning a BA in Visual Arts and an MA and an MPhil in Public Art, he is currently completing his PhD in Public Art supported by a scholarship from the Jumex Foundation.

He is a veteran of many courses and workshops and also teaches both in the UK and overseas in his areas of speciality. Pablo is a member of some professional associations and a founding member of the Free University Collective of Art Theory and Research, the Circular Workshop of Graphic Production, the Autonomous Gallery in the National School of Plastic Arts and of the self-managed cultural centre The Three in Valencia.

Contact: pablolugo@hotmail.com

Unit 24, 7 Fountayne Rd. N15 4QL

London, United Kingdom

+44(0)7582030826

www.pablolugo.com

Instagram @polhaygnes